

CAUSES OF NEGATIVE CHANGES IN CHILDREN'S BEHAVIOR

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Annotation :Mediation is a specific type of activity of social importance and is an active relationship formed on the basis of recognition of basic freedoms. This article talks about the formation and development of tolerant attitude in resolving conflicts among students.

Key word: Meditation, xenophobia, society, conflictology, psychology, antic, method.

The achievement of any society is to raise a physically and spiritually mature generation. However, due to various reasons and factors, in some cases there are violations and gaps in the upbringing of young people. What is worrying is that the decrease in such negative situations is almost imperceptible. This, in turn, has a negative impact on the development of society. The behavior of young people begins to form from early childhood. The process of forming children's behavior is a rather complex process, which requires adults to be extremely responsible and attentive. Because it is in this process that the mistakes of adults can harm the child's future and make it difficult for the child to find his place in society. In the process of conducting this study, we tried to study the causes and factors of negative changes in children's behavior.

According to the Head of State, young people are inclined to think in new ways, boldly come up with new ideas and implement them, and solve problems based on creative and non-standard approaches. Therefore, today we attach priority to creating all the conditions for the younger generation to gain knowledge, reveal their talents and potential in the fields of science, innovation, literature, art and sports, and actively participate in the socio-political life of our society. One of the

blessed hadiths collected by our grandfather Imam Bukhari states: “Knowledge learned in youth is like a pattern carved in stone.” It is well known from history that our great scholars, following such wisdom, made great discoveries in the field of science and made an incomparable contribution to the development of universal thinking. Continuing such blessed traditions and raising new Khorezmians, Ferghanis, Berunis, Ibn Sina, Mirzo Ulugbeks, and Navais in our country is not only our task, but also our sacred duty to history and the future”[10; 1]. In order to fulfill this duty, it is necessary to pay attention to the issue of properly educating young people from childhood and raising them to be mentally stable at the level of state policy.

As we know, the personality of a preschool child is formed under the influence of the reality surrounding him. As a result, he begins to understand socially significant tasks, enters into independent relations with other members of the community, and thus the socialization of the child's personality occurs. At the same time, the child's personality is formed as a result of the assimilation of elements of social experience. That is, this process occurs with the repetition, imitation, and assimilation of the actions of adults by children. As an objective factor, B. Umarov previously proposed this idea states: “As objective reasons, an unhealthy environment in society, conditions, economic and political instability, socio-psychological conditions in small social groups, relationships with people...”[91; 2] Since there is an unhealthy environment in social life, changes in the behavior of preschool children also occur primarily under the influence of the unhealthy environment surrounding them. It is known that the family is the first center of socialization for the child. It is in this center that the child begins to interact with the social environment, assimilates social norms and values in society. As the child grows up in the family, he observes the relationships between adults and takes a model from them. Based on this, the child’s behavior is formed. This or that form of relations between parents, that is, peace or disagreement in the family, the nature

of relations between brothers and sisters, determine the child's behavior is among the contributing factors.

In particular, family conflicts occur as a result of the inappropriate behavior of one of the parents and their indifference and harshness towards the upbringing of the child. In this regard, it is enough to look at the research of the famous psychologist Gotting. In his opinion, problems and conflicts in families cause aggression in children, especially the fact that they grow up to be violent, angry, and rude. According to Gotting's conclusions, in conflict families, the main attention is paid to mutual conflicts, and child upbringing remains threats and punishment [99;3]

Caring for the future generation, striving to raise and raise a physically and spiritually healthy generation is one of our national characteristics. Similarly, this is an important task facing every family and society today. Parents live with the dream of having and raising a child, they want him to become a mature person, a perfect person in the future. This issue is the duty of every teacher and educational institution to society, and teachers, like parents, encourage their students to maturity. So, a smart child is not only the happiness of parents, but also of teachers, and of society and the country. Therefore, "it is absolutely impossible to look at such an important and strategic issue as education in the old way, to approach it with old knowledge and systems. If we do not create the most modern and advanced system in this regard, we will not be able to solve any of the problems that lie before us" [9;4]. These works cannot be implemented "without completely changing the attitude of society to education".

Psychologist B. Umarov, in his methodological manual "Advice to Parents on Child Education Disorders and Their Prevention," divides the causes of changes in children's behavior into subjective and objective factors, and includes the following in the subjective causes: "The subjective causes of behavioral deviations include the interests and needs of the adolescent, his worldview and spiritual world,

goals and directions, values, legal consciousness, life plans, lifestyle and motives. The subjective conditions include the demographic and socio-psychological characteristics of the population, in particular, ethnopsychological aspects, character, temperament, age and gender. The objective causes are an unhealthy environment, conditions, economic and political instability in society, socio-psychological conditions in small social groups, and relationships with people.” Similarly, we have included problems in the process of forming the child's personality, the characteristics of their temperament, among the subjective factors of negative changes in the behavior of preschool children.

Another scientist L. Stone bases the reason for negative changes in the behavior of children on the fact that they seek from someone the true maternal love that is necessary during puberty. The researcher believes that, according to their social background, the "I" of children is born under the influence of the assessment of their behavior by adults and is constantly being formed. That is, "... the role of loved ones forms an "emotional environment", a "mental space" in the development of positive qualities in the child's behavior and the implementation of self-expression processes," he writes. From the above approaches, it can be seen that the behavior of children is influenced to a certain extent by the social environment, the power of psychologically balanced situations.

OpinionAlso, the researcher, Golfarb, attributes the negative changes in the child's behavior to the reality of infancy. In his opinion, children separated from their parents have difficulty interacting with the world around them, their speech development lags behind their peers, which causes them to feel hopeless, depressed, and timid. According to another scientist, L.N. Galiguzova, the child's behavior is formed and develops under the influence of interaction. Because the need for interaction in the development of a child is observed from infancy. The baby's interaction with his parents and loved ones also affects his behavior. The emergence of his interaction with his parents is manifested in the following cases: being able

to look at the faces of loved ones, hearing the voices of his parents, recognizing them by their voices, responding to the actions of loved ones, laughing, crying. In these processes, the care and affection of loved ones for the child, the attention when the child laughs and cries, are the foundation for the formation of the child's behavior. Also, according to his point of view, the processes of emotional interaction with the child during infancy lay the foundation for the child's self-awareness under certain conditions. That is, this situation begins to manifest itself in the children's feeling of well-being, cheerfulness, enthusiasm, inquisitiveness, and curiosity. Gradually, as a result of constant interaction with loved ones, babies learn to act cooperatively, accept parental assessments and act according to the model. This, in turn, leads to an acceleration in the development of a person's self-awareness. The experience of positive interaction with parents begins to manifest itself as human qualities appear during the period when babies begin to interact with each other. The baby's positive interactions with loved ones create the initial stages of such characteristics as enthusiasm, interest, courage, self-confidence, and activity. American psychologist G.F. Harlow also emphasized that the affection of the mother when holding her child in her arms is as important for the child's emotional state as breast milk is for the child's physical development, and he also showed that the relationship between parents and children is important for the child's psyche. He also believes that the formation of feelings of affection and connection between parents and children from early childhood determines the child's life path, his future emotional and mental world. American psychologist K. Izard draws attention to emotional states in children in his research. In his opinion, the following main emotions (feelings) are manifested in children. These are: joy, surprise, sadness, anger, disgust, respect, shame, curiosity, excitement and guilt. As the causes of these emotions, he identifies the subject's feelings related to the environment and individual processes that can cause emotions. Another American child psychotherapist, V. Oaklander, in his research, examines the negative traits

found in children: aggression, irritability, fear, autism, hyperactivity and alienation. In his observations, he paid attention to the specific behavioral problems of children. He admits that the roots of these problems may lie in family relationships, children's interactions with adults, and children's adaptation to the community. He presents to the general public the goals and means of providing therapeutic assistance to children with various forms of emotional changes.

One of the famous Japanese figures, one of the founders of SONY, Masaru Ibuka, in his treatise "It's Late After Three," highlighted the importance of the child's relationship with his parents and family members in the formation of a child's behavior and spiritual development. M. Ibuka shows that the establishment of emotional relationships between parents and children depends on the ability to form an emotional state in the child, that is, on the parents' approach to the child and their skills. This situation is also considered the main source of the formation of the child's communicative qualities. In the family, as a result of parents' trusting attitude towards their child and their support for his/her actions, the child develops the qualities of openness, quick communication, a democratic way of parent-child relationships, and the formation of communicative qualities. The "authoritarian" way of parent-child relationships leads to increased emotional sensitivity, traumatization of the child's soul, indecisiveness in behavior, and the "little unsuccessful" way of parents' attitude towards their child has a negative effect on the child's behavior.

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